

Crisis Navigator for Rapid Mobilisation of Science Communication

For Civil Society
Actors

Trust

Values and Emotion

Ethical issues

Framing and Sensemaking

Trust & Collaboration

Power

Collaboration

Reflective practice

Pre-Crisis

Imminent Crisis

Actual Crisis

Post-Crisis

Introduction

The **Crisis Navigator** is designed as a **strategic resource for diverse science communication stakeholders who communicate science in times of crises**. Rather than offering standardized guidelines (“what to do”), the Crisis Navigator functions as a **sensitising tool** – a conceptual and practical aid that helps communicators notice, reflect on, and interpret subtle aspects of their work. In this case, the guiding question is: **What are crucial considerations for civil society actors who need to communicate about science during crises?**

This present tool is targeted towards **civil society actors**, including but not limited to non-governmental organizations (NGOs), citizen representatives, and advocacy groups. Their work may include fostering public participation in decision-making processes and challenging the dominance of expert-driven narratives by highlighting alternative perspectives. Their ability to **engage communities, challenge dominant narratives, and advocate for policy change** makes them essential during times of crisis.

The Crisis Navigator is structured along four stages: pre-, imminent, actual, and post-crisis, taking into account the **evolving dynamics of a crisis**. Ultimately, this Crisis Navigator serves as **a guide for civil society actors to better imagine and anticipate what they are – and could be – up against when communicating science in times of crisis**, supporting them to navigate their practice in a more informed and reflective manner.

Challenge: Complexity and uncertainty

GUIDING QUESTION

What are good ways to convey the current state of knowledge and uncertainty to broader publics?

To answer the guiding question, consider:

Information gaps: Civil society actors should identify and monitor what information is available to whom, where and when; and what gaps exist or may arise in understanding the situation before, during, and after communicating. When a crisis is imminent, misinformation tends to spread rapidly as uncertainty grows and people may seek explanations or reassurance. Rumors, speculation, and emotionally charged content often fill information gaps before verified facts are available. In such situations, civil society actors should communicate early, clearly, and consistently, providing verified information through trusted channels and acknowledging what is still unknown.

Science and evidence: How complex is the science? What is the evidence? Civil society actors should aim to integrate multiple perspectives in response to these questions to offer a balanced and comprehensive understanding of an issue, while acknowledging limitations and areas of ongoing research or debate. Most importantly, engaging openly with experts, the media, and the public about these questions of expertise and evidence can help sustain trust and legitimacy, which are essential for collective action in times of crisis.

Voice: Who is able to influence the state of knowledge? Who is seen as credible or trustworthy? Which voices deserve to be acknowledged, heard, and/or given a public platform – and which ones do not? Weigh the pros and cons of giving voice to particular stakeholders and types of knowledge in society, while providing opportunities for collective exploration of scientific topics.

Clarity and simplicity: The communication of uncertainty and complexity requires clear and concise language that is accessible to a broad audience, and that avoids jargon and technical terms whenever possible. Ideally, this language breaks down concepts into understandable and relatable explanations, even complex and uncertain concepts.

Collaboration

GUIDING QUESTION

How can civil society actors facilitate constructive exchanges between concerned stakeholders?

To ensure a coordinated and effective response, collaboration is essential. Civil society actors can act as a vehicle to bring scientific knowledge to politicians, and should therefore foster trust and understanding by interacting with scientists from various fields of study, (local) governments and policy makers. By working on these collaborative efforts already during the pre-crisis phase, multi- or interdisciplinary expert networks can be established that allow rapid mobilization of expertise when needed. Such collaboration reduces fragmented expertise and narrative gaps in science communication during crises. By bringing together scientists, policymakers, journalists, and practitioners, such collaboration fosters more coherent and context-sensitive messaging. However, differences in language and professional norms can hinder mutual understanding and timely information exchange, making deliberate coordination, trust building and clear allocation of responsibilities essential.

Trust

GUIDING QUESTION

How can civil society actors enable, preserve, and build trust in times of crisis?

Communicating science in times of crisis as a civil society actor should be focused on building and nurturing trust. Civil society actors can build trust by creating spaces for open dialogues with affected communities, representing those whose perspectives are often overlooked. Although trust is an important theme throughout all phases of crisis, it is challenging to set up participatory activities (shown to increase trust) such as citizen dialogues during the actual crisis or imminent crisis phase. Pre-crisis efforts should therefore include participatory platforms to build and uphold mutual understanding and acknowledgement of personal situations and emotions. By focusing on the issues of trust and collaboration already during the pre-crisis phase, a solid foundation can be set which ensures effective science communication when a crisis hits.

Values and emotions

GUIDING QUESTION

What is the role of values and emotions in science communication – and how do we engage with values and emotions productively?

Values and emotions are a key to exploring and communicating the complexity of crises and urgent societal problems. On the one hand, emotions are an important source of information about the values at stake in times of crises. On the other hand, giving space to emotions and values in communication can render it more effective because it enables connecting with audiences and spurs action. By connecting with values and emotions through interaction with general publics and civil society already before a crisis hits, trust and collaboration can also be upheld during crises. In the work of civil society actors, more specifically, connecting to values and emotions plays an important role in advocating for change. It is these actors that can guarantee involvement underrepresented groups or issues in science communication practices and decision making during crises.

Power

GUIDING QUESTION

Who has the ability to influence, shape, and control the framing and sensemaking of stakeholders and publics?

Crises require rapid decision-making to mobilize necessary stakeholders and processes, often leading to top-down policy approaches that limit bottom-up decision making and overlook valuable knowledge of stakeholders such as local residents or civil society. Therefore, awareness of power dynamics is necessary. Here, 'power' refers to the ability to influence, shape, and control the framing and sensemaking of stakeholders. Civil society actors play an essential role in addressing inequalities, recognizing community values, and ensuring these values are not overlooked by those with decision-making power. Recognizing and navigating these power dynamics is crucial for ethical and effective communication of science that promotes informed decision-making, equity and public trust.

Ethical issues

GUIDING QUESTION

How can civil society actors promote an ethically-sound and responsible crisis response?

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Framing and Sensemaking

GUIDING QUESTION

How do different stakeholders frame and make sense of scientific information and science communication?

Whereas framing refers to the way information is presented, sense-making is about how individuals make sense of the information they receive. Through framing, it is possible as a sender to emphasize certain aspects of a topic while downplaying others, and influence how an audience perceives, understands, and reacts to scientific information. Through storytelling, value-based messaging and a narrative that includes public values and interests, civil society actors can connect scientific topics to people's lived experiences. Yet, this does not mean that through framing civil society actors are able to fully control how their audiences make sense of scientific knowledge. The ways in which science is communicated can help different audiences to make sense of scientific information in times of crises by highlighting contradictions and inherent uncertainties in an easy-to-understand way, and by connecting to different personal situations and social contexts, and by tailoring messages to cultural values and beliefs.

Reflective practice

GUIDING QUESTION

How can civil society actors continuously learn from, and adapt to, crisis situations?

It is helpful for civil society actors to regularly self-reflect on their science communication activities during any of the crisis stages. Whether this entails advocating for overlooked minorities or issues during a crisis, or involving certain publics pre-crisis to build trust, every action is one to reflect on and learn from. Reflective practice means adopting a critical and reflective stance to responses in specific situations, and to understand how these responses are shaped by frames of thought, emotions, assumptions and world-views. This can help to become sensitive to one's own position and assumptions when it comes to tensions and underlying conflicts that may be exacerbated in times of crises. Insights gained from this reflection can help strengthen strategies in future crises.

Trust & Collaborations

GUIDING QUESTION

How can civil society actors build trust and facilitate constructive exchanges?

Similar to the pre-crisis phase, it is essential to build both trust and collaboration during the post-crisis phase; and it is crucial to repair and restore trust where it was lost or damaged. This is probably the best way to ensure rapid mobilization and effective science communication during possible future crises. It is helpful here to compare and contrast communication approaches in other crisis contexts, paying attention not only to visible manifestations of a communication crisis (e.g., misinformation, disinformation), but also to structural factors (e.g., inequitable access to information) and cultural factors (e.g., symbolic framings, such as "ignorant publics") that may or may not be used to justify structural exclusions.

Deliverable 2.1 Science Communication Rapid Mobilisation Roadmap

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